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Recommendations for Improving the Quality of Preschool Education through an Assessment System

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Annotation: This article discusses recommendations for improving the quality of preschool education through an assessment system. The problem of improving the quality of preschool education is very relevant in modern conditions of modernization of the preschool education system and requires management decisions at various levels of the preschool education system.

Keywords: recommendation, quality improvement, preschool education, assessment.

The main task of the state educational policy of the Republic in the context of the modernization of the education system is to ensure the modern quality of education, including preschool. The system of preschool education is currently actively developing. Modern society makes new demands on preschool educational institutions, on the organization of the educational process in them, on the choice and justification of the content of basic and partial curricula, the results and effectiveness of their activities, the selection and training of teaching staff. One of the main goals of the Ilk Kadam program for preschool education is to provide state guarantees for the level and quality of education based on the unity of mandatory requirements for the conditions for the implementation of basic educational programs, their structure and the results of their development. The quality of preschool education is a characteristic of the system of preschool education, reflecting the degree of compliance of the actual educational results achieved with regulatory requirements, social and personal expectations. The problem of improving the quality of preschool education is very relevant in modern conditions of modernization of the preschool education system and requires management decisions at various levels of the preschool education system. An indispensable condition for the validity of these decisions is reliable information: - on the quality of preschool education; - about the main trends regarding the quality of educational services for children of preschool age in a preschool educational institution; - on the compliance of the education provided with modern ideas about the quality of preschool education.

In this regard, it can be stated that the strategic goal of improving the system for assessing the quality of preschool education is to optimize the quality management of preschool education. It follows from this that improving the quality of preschool education requires improving the system of its assessment, which should meaningfully (in accordance with modern ideas about the values of the development of a child of preschool age) and organizationally regulate the processes of ensuring and improving the quality of preschool education through procedures for assessing this quality. At the same time, the assessment of the quality of preschool education is considered in the interests of the individual, society, the state, and the system itself.

Quality management of preschool education required the identification of problems in the activities of public organizations that require increased attention:

- creation of appropriate conditions for organizational learning of preschoolers;

- organization of analytical activities and scientific and methodological support for assessing the quality of preschool education; -
updating the managed and managing subsystems of the TOE;
- development of a new practice of preschool education through scientifically based support of experimental activities. The quality of education in our kindergarten is considered as the degree of compliance of the totality of properties and results of the education of preschool children with the predicted goals of the development of the educational institution based on the Ilk Kadam program, the needs and expectations of the participants in the educational process. From this point of view, the quality of education is considered as a combination of three components:
 - the quality of the educational process;
 - the quality of the conditions for the implementation of educational activities;
 - the quality of the results. One of the components of the quality of education in our PA is the educational process, which has its own specific control levers.

First of all, the educational process is carried out in the conditions of developing interaction between the participants in the educational process and the management of its quality and involves the impact on its components - target, content, activity, and effectiveness. This means that increasing the effectiveness of ongoing activities will depend on the quality of the educational work of adults (teachers and parents) and the child's own activities at each stage of the educational process.

To improve the quality of the conditions for the implementation of educational activities, we have identified the following areas:

- financing (involves the definition of flexible funding standards, the transition to equity financing, monitoring the spending of budget funds);
- staffing (involves the development of a system of staffing and improving the professional competence of teachers through the organization of a system of advanced training and self-education).

And, finally, solving the problem of managing the quality of the conditions of preschool education requires raising the level of managerial culture of leaders in the assessment of education: creating conditions for improving the quality of the educational process in assessing education, mastering the technology of managing the quality of work.

Our institution uses: technology of education management based on results Determining the main goals of the development of their preschool educational institution, each leader, together with the teaching staff, organizes the entire pedagogical process, which means that he constantly compares the results obtained with the planned ones. This requires making prompt decisions on the situation, i.e. for specific results. project management technology, which considers project management as the management of education assessment in the conditions of an innovative mode of functioning. Ultimately, regardless of the priority technology for managing the quality of education assessment, the main problem remains the creation of a model for assessing the quality of preschool education. This problem increases if we consider the evaluation of education in the mode of development, that is, assuming constant changes in the goal of each stage of development of the evaluation of education in accordance with the results of the pedagogical process. Assessment of the quality of the results of the educational process is the most discussed topic today.

The model for assessing the quality of preschool education includes: goals, content, organizational structure, pedagogical mechanisms for systemic correction of the educational process, which allow to realize the regulatory and marketing goals of education assessment in partnership interaction of all subjects. Improving the quality of preschool education is possible through the integrated use of the main methodological approaches to assessing the quality of education.

1. The axiological approach to assessment provides for an analysis of the values that are the basis for determining the structure and content of the system for assessing the quality of preschool education. The basis of the modern state policy of the Republic in the field of preschool education is based on the ideas of humanization, therefore, the main professional and pedagogical value in determining the indicators for assessing the quality of preschool education within the framework of this approach is the child.

2. The sociocultural approach to assessing the quality of education in the assessment of education is determined by the nature of the interaction of children with adults, with other children, with the object-spatial world. The level of independent behavior and its ability to solve everyday life situations are assessed; social competence in communicating with other children and adults.

3. The competency-based approach is promising, because in the context of modern ideas about the purpose of education, key competencies are relevant for preschoolers and fix the degree of their readiness to be included in a new school life.

When assessing the quality of education within the framework of this approach, the degree of mastery of competencies (intellectual, linguistic, social and physical) is identified, as well as ways of behavior (arbitrariness, independence, initiative, creativity, ability to choose) and its attitude towards oneself (image of oneself, level of self-esteem, the presence or absence of self-esteem). The complex application of the described approaches makes the problem of assessing and measuring the development of a child fundamentally solvable and allows parents (non-specialists) to be involved in assessing the quality of education as independent subjects of assessment.

The model for assessing the quality of preschool education in education assessment is a set of interconnected functions, an object, subjects and subject of assessment, indicators and criteria, procedures and results of assessment. Developing the problems of scientific and methodological assurance of the quality of preschool education, we pay attention to the compliance of the assessment of the quality of preschool education with the goals of the upbringing and development of preschool children, the educational standard, and the needs of consumers of educational services.

Functions for assessing the quality of preschool education:

1. Instructive - methodological function is to create regulations for the evaluation of institutions of various forms that implement programs of preschool education.

2. The control function includes carrying out evaluation procedures in individual educational institutions and organizations.

3. The analytical function includes the collection and analysis of data on the assessment of education, building on this basis a rating of institutions implementing preschool education programs in terms of the "quality of education" parameter.

4. The information function can solve three problems. Firstly, the information is addressed to the pedagogical community in order to form modern ideas about the quality of education in education assessment. Secondly, the information is addressed to parents, for whom it can become the basis for choosing the form and place of receiving preschool education for the child. Thirdly, one of the tasks

of informing about the results of the quality assessment may be the coordination of the efforts of the kindergarten and the school.

Objects, subjects and subject of assessment: When assessing the quality of education, it is necessary to clearly define what is being assessed (object), who evaluates (subject) and why evaluates (subject). In this regard, the assessment of the quality of education (the system of assessments) should be divided into assessments of the quality of education from the external environment (that is, assessments of consumers of educational services) and internal assessments of the quality in the education system itself. The whole set of approaches to the selection of evaluation parameters can be reduced to the following five clusters:

1. Educational activities. The level of quality of educational programs and their methodological support is assessed, the content of which allows teachers to build an educational process in accordance with modern requirements and the level of development of society and at the same time without undue burden for pupils.
2. Development environment. The degree of enrichment of the object-spatial environment is assessed, the filling of which provides the child with opportunities for self-development. The indicators are the quantitative ratio of "teacher-children", the education and professional experience of the teaching staff, the features of the room in which the children are.
3. Psychological comfort of the child. Only good, ie. meaningful, varied education, focused on child development, can give a positive quality of pedagogical work. The level of ensuring the psychological comfort of the child in an educational institution is assessed in order to preserve his physical and mental health. The most optimal characteristics of the behavior of an educator who provides quality support are: a responsible position, acceptance of the child, meaningful communication, and the ability to empathize.
4. Health saving activities. The good quality of the physical context of a child's life in an institution is determined not by the number of objects, but by their quality, diversity, clearly structured space, its stimulating influence. The quality of the use of health-saving educational technologies is being assessed, which allow organizing the process of education in assessing education in such a way that the child can participate in educational activities without excessive physical and mental stress that undermines health.
5. Satisfying the needs of the family and the child in the services of a preschool educational institution. Thus, we can distinguish the following integral criteria for assessing a preschool educational institution, which determine the quality of preschool education:
 - ensuring the well-being of the child, his comfortable stay in kindergarten;
 - the readiness of the kindergarten to preserve the health of the child, to ensure the necessary correction of developmental deficiencies;
 - focus of preschool education on the child's success at the next stage of education;
 - meeting the needs of the family and the child in the services of preschool educational institutions.

Solving the problems of improving the quality of preschool education in the evaluation of education requires a systematic approach to its evaluation. An important condition for objectivity is the systematic and regular procedures for collecting and examining data on the quality of the educational activities of a preschool institution. Assessment Methods The main assessment methods are as follows:

1. study of the presented materials of introspection, regulatory legal documentation;
2. analysis of software, educational, methodological and staffing of the declared focus of the educational program;
3. observation;
4. study of the subject-developing environment, as well as conditions that ensure maximum satisfaction of the needs of the parents of pupils;
5. analysis of planning, diagnostic results.

Stages of assessment The assessment of the quality of preschool education in the assessment of education includes several stages:

1. selection of quality indicators;
2. definition of evaluation criteria (reference, requirement or standard), based on
3. what this indicator will be assessed for;
4. formation of a scale of levels of achievement of the quality criterion;
5. development of tools;
6. organization of collection, processing, analysis, interpretation of the received data;
7. presentation and dissemination of generalized information for different categories of users;
8. organizing a wide public and professional discussion;
9. preparation of recommendations for improving the education system and management decision-making.

Evaluation results. A generalized assessment is made in several assessed areas:

1. the level of implementation of the educational program of the corresponding focus;
2. the level of organization of the subject-developing environment, the assessment of education, taking into account the declared focus of the educational program;
3. the nature of the interaction of teachers with children.
4. Prospective correlation of the results achieved in the assessment of education with a modeled portrait of a child aged 6.5–7 years, at the exit from preschool education.

Targeting of the evaluation results:

1. teaching staff of institutions implementing the main general educational program of preschool education and responsible for its successful (effective) implementation;
2. parents of a child mastering the basic general educational program of preschool education;
3. heads of institutions implementing the main general educational program of preschool education.

The proposed model improves the quality of education on the basis of maintaining its fundamentality and compliance with the current and future needs of the individual and society as a whole.

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